

Energy Transition Pathways for Zambia: A Modelling Approach Using OseMOSYS

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Energy Modelling Platform Global (EMP-G)

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CONTEXT

- In 2020, Zambia's electricity demand was projected to double from **2,143 MW** to **4,169 MW** by 2040, largely driven by domestic customers at an annual growth of 1.3%
- Currently, Zambia's installed capacity is **3,811.3 MW** with Hydro accounting for over 80%
- To improve the generation mix, Zambia has set a national target to integrate 30% of VRES by 2030

Research Questions

1. What are the potential impacts of maintaining the current energy policy on Zambia's energy mix and sustainability targets?
2. How will Zambia's energy landscape evolve if the government successfully implements its policy to achieve at least 30% of electricity production from VRES by 2030?
3. How could recurrent drought conditions influence Zambia's energy security of its electricity supply, particularly in terms of hydropower dependence?

Source: 2020 Zambia Electricity Cost of Service Study Report - Load Forecast

1

Business As Usual (BAU)

This scenario assumes continuation of current policies and trends without significant changes in the energy mix or policy interventions.

2

VRES Integration Scenario (REW)

This scenario models the effects of a policy initiative by the Zambian government that mandates at least 30% of the country's nominal electricity production to come from utility-scale solar and wind power by 2030.

3

Drought Impact Scenario (DIS)

This scenario considers the historical and projected impacts of drought on Zambia's energy system. It models reduced water availability for hydropower generation, analyzing how such conditions affect energy security, supply reliability, and the potential need for alternative energy sources or system adaptations.

SCENARIOS

POWER GENERATION

INSTALLED CAPACITY

- Coal Power Plant
- Gas Power Plant (SCGT)
- Off-grid Hydropower
- Solar PV (Utility)
- Electricity Imports
- Large Hydropower Plant (Dam) (>100MW)
- Onshore Wind
- Gas Power Plant (CCGT)
- Medium Hydropower Plant (10-100MW)
- Small Hydropower Plant (<10MW)

TOTAL COST

Total Cost (MUSD)

EMISSIONS

— Total CO2 Emissions - BAU — Total CO2 Emissions - REW — Total CO2 Emissions - DIS

Conclusion

Key Findings:

- BAU is cost-effective but risky due to reliance on hydropower.
- REW integrates renewables, reducing emissions and enhancing security at a higher cost.
- DIS is the most expensive but offers the best protection against climate risks.

Investing in renewables and resilience is crucial for Zambia's long-term energy sustainability and security, despite the higher initial costs.

Policy Insights:

- **Renewable Integration:** Support solar PV and wind to meet the 30% target by 2030.
- **IRP Review:** Review IRP results to align with OSeMOSYS results.
- **Climate Resilience:** Incorporate climate risks into energy planning.
- **Off-Grid Solutions:** Promote off-grid systems to enhance rural access.

Future Work:

- **Climate Risk Modeling:** Expand to include extreme weather events.
- **Economic Analysis:** Assess the feasibility of large-scale energy storage.
- **Decentralized Systems:** Explore microgrids for improved access and resilience.
- **Policy Challenges:** Address barriers to successful policy implementation.

THANK YOU